

Startup Entrepreneurs in India: Challenges and Opportunities

Dr. Vishal Singh¹, Dr. Abhishek Kumar², Mr. Chandan Sonkar³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, T.D.P.G. College, Jaunpur, U.P.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Vidyant Hindu P.G. College, Lucknow, U.P.

³Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, T.D.P.G. College, Jaunpur, U.P.

ABSTRACT

Startup Program is recognized as a panacea for the economic development in India. We have realized that the government has facilitation of business establishment and empowerment of entrepreneurs on the top of its development agenda. While there is optimism building towards creating new businesses. World Bank has recorded that the India is one of the most difficult countries in the world to start a business. It takes approximately 30 days for someone to start a business in India versus one day in New Zealand. Apart from rigid structure and bureaucracy that exists in starting their business, startup entrepreneurs face several challenges and hurdles along the path to growth. This paper makes an attempt to find out the challenges and opportunities that occurred during their journey. The present study is descriptive in nature.

Key Words : Panacea, Economic Development, Bureaucracy, Startup Entrepreneur.

INTRODUCTION

India is now the fourth largest startup hub in the world. Startups have continued to play significant roles in the growth, development and industrialization of many economies in all over the world. Globally technology based startup companies are registering in higher number than non-high tech companies because of their growing importance in new knowledge economy.

The aim of this study is to discuss about the upcoming opportunities available to youth because of digitalization. With the advancements in marketing in the form of digital marketing, scope and career opportunities are increasing. Depending on the innovativeness of an individual, one can execute digital marketing strategies. One can start as fresher and without any experience. The innovative ideas and work will provide a competitive edge in the market. Opportunities increase as a resultant of dynamic environment and hence new people with striking and innovative ideas can make it big in no time. Things change faster in the digital world as compared to the old business processes.

Many entrepreneurs are excited by the announcement made by Hon'ble Prime Minister as part of the startup India action plan. There is no doubt the measures are significant, but they do beg the question, are all the startups really eligible for the benefits that are announced? The reason is that the road to building startup in India is filled with hurdles and challenges. Hence this paper will try to highlight the challenges and opportunities of startup entrepreneurs in India.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

(1) **Thomas Astebro and Irwin Bernhardt (2017)**. He has found that there is a negative correlation between having a bank loan and business survival and a positive correlation between having a non-bank loan and business survival. However having a bank loan remains a good predictor of the survival of startup companies otherwise.

(2) **Thomas Hell Mann and Manju Puri (2014)**. In their paper examine empirical evidence on the impact that venture capitalists can have on the development path of new firms. They used a hand collected data set on Silicon Valley startup companies and analysed the influence of venture capital on the professionalization of firms internal organization. The evidence suggest that there is a "soft facet to venture capitalist, in terms of supporting companies to build up their human resource in organization."

(3) **David B. Andretsch, Enrico Santarelli and Marco Vivarelli, (2005)**. The aim of this paper is to shed some light on

industry dynamics in Italy. For this purpose, they used a large and comprehensive longitudinal data base, identifying the startup of new manufacturing firms and their subsequent post entry performance. The enable them to link the survival and growth of firms in each manufacturing industry specifically to their startup size.

(4) **Christopher A. Pissarides (2001)**. In his paper, he has studied the role of company startup costs for employment performance. The model is search equilibrium with a new concept for firms. Agents have an innate managerial ability and make a career choice to become either managers or workers. Managers setup firms, post jobs and match with workers. There is a unique equilibrium career choice, which is also optimal if the wage rule internalizes the search externalities.

(5) **Gavin C. Reid (1999)**. He has found that surviving firms were larger, better funded, lower geared and more profit oriented. They also paid higher wages and were both more attuned to and realistic about, new technologies. The conclusion formed was that firms which survival generally displayed wider and deeper competencies than firms which closed.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To know the concept of startup program.
- To find out the challenges and opportunities of startup entrepreneurs in India.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study deals with various aspect of startup entrepreneurs as well as challenges and opportunities of startup entrepreneurs in India. The study is based on descriptive research design. Data have been collected through secondary sources like as books, newspapers, articles, websites, magazines etc. This paper is also based on our personal experience and interaction with people in the society.

CONCEPT OF STARTUP PROGRAM

The startups are usually those enterprises which are promoted by first timer entrepreneurs and are relatively recent in origin. The entrepreneur or a team of entrepreneurs having expertise experience, knowledge or know how etc., are usually the driving force behind such ventures involving a high degree of entrepreneurial skill and risk taking capacity. Such startups need support and encouragement from various perspective during the initial phase and subsequently the growth phase till establishment on firm-footing.

There are lots of e-Commerce sites and online businesses is much higher as compared to the previous decade. Learning digital marketing will facilitate upcoming entrepreneurs and bloggers as well as individual will also get good jobs.

In short, startup renders a lot of opportunities for fresher's as well as entrepreneurs. Students who are seeking innovative careers may take up startup business as the next career option and may unlock their strengths. With time, entire world will get digitalized, and companies will focus on techno savvy users.

CHALLENGES BEFORE INDIAN STARTUP ENTREPRENEURS

(1) Building a team :

The most of the Indian focus on getting a regular job with a big brand improves career growth more than startup. Also, job security plays a vital role in decision making. Working in a larger organization is more secure and socially valuable than working in startups. It is commonto see people working in startups being pressured from home to take up better jobs with larger organization. Moreover, employee benefits are also minimum in startups when compared to big corporations. Hence getting the right talent become challenging.

(2) Selling is hard :

It is hard to break into the Indian market with a consumer product. People are substantially price sensitive and competition is fierce. Therefore, selling premium product becomes a hard task. Moreover, when a startups aim to do a B2B sale, the decision making process to buy the product is very slow and may take several months. For example- for selling software to Banks and government, or larger organizations, people may send the quote, keep following for a months, and then end up with a "No Thanks". It primarily happens because of poor decision making process in companies and a "playing it safe" attitude. Hence the risk factor is remain exists.

(3) Rules and Regulations :

According to the latest tax policy, startup firms are mandated to pay income tax on the premium they have charges over fair market, while selling shares to unregistered investors, including pvt.equity and venture funds. Though this aim to stop money laundering, analyst says it will affect the investment scenario for startups. Moreover, to register our startup takes a minimum of two to six months.

Although the road to launch and get started with a startup company is difficult things are progressing interestingly. Passionate and ambitious people are finding their inroads to their entrepreneurial calling and working their way around hurdles to create success for themselves.

(4) Lack of Reliable Mentors :

Mentors prepare young entrepreneurs to fight on the edge and also smoothen their trail of navigating through the right network. Successful entrepreneurs who have learnt a great deal from their failures provide proven insights to the budding ones. The human capital required to nurture entrepreneurs are yet to be seasoned in India. Though business networks offer access to some big names, people with specialized skill sets would always add value. This comes down to the challenge of getting in contact with the right kind of people who has in-depth knowledge on the areas concerning the startup.

(5) Location:

The most important problem faced by an Indian startup is the location from where it is being launched. India is a place of varied culture and taste, thus, every product might not be welcomed equally by every region. A survey was found out that 42% of the failed startups attribute their failure to the lack of their market need. Now, this is where we shouldn't follow Steve Jobs' suggestion of 'not asking what the customer wants.

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(6) Marketing Strategy:

This follows the above challenge. Just like the fact that every product is not meant for every location, every marketing strategy wouldn't work for every region. Poor marketing is the reason behind the failed startups.

(7) Management of resources right from the beginning:

Once the business starts flourishing, it gets all the more important to manage the inflow, investment in an organized way as there would soon be generated too many data to handle. Every small bit of mismanagement would amplify as the company would grow and things can get real messy and out of proportion.

(8) Fighting demotivation:

This gets more important when it comes to Indian startups because in many regions here the idea of students choosing an unconventional path is still perceived as destroying one's career.

(9) Transformational and insecurity effect :

Rural entrepreneurship is not always directly related to income. It can also refer to an intense level of insecurity. Many times those who have managed to improve their position are pressed back down again by natural disasters, inflation and other shocks. Some aspects of globalization increase such problems. Globalization is generally associated with the accelerated pace of change in economic life and increased competitive pressures. This requires a speedy adaptation, which may simply be outside the range of those with few modern skills or other assets. As indicated earlier, globalization is linked to increased specialization, but this, for all its advantages, increases risks for entrepreneurs by pushing them to 'play all their cards'. These factors are further compounded by the transformational and insecurity effect due to volatile environment.

(10) Family Challenges:

Convincing to opt for business over job is easy is not an easy task for an individual. The first thing compared is – Will you make more money in the business of your choice or as a successor of family business. This is where it becomes almost impossible to convince that you can generate more cash with your passion than doing what your Dad is doing.

(11) Social Challenges:

Family challenges are always at the top because that is what matter the most but at times social challenges also are very important. Let us say we and our friend graduated at the same time. We opted for entrepreneurship and our friend opted for a job. He now has a flat, car and what not because he could easily get those with a bank loan but we still have nothing to show off and this is where the challenge comes.

(12) Technological Challenges:

Indian education system lags too much from the Job industry as a whole but then it lags even more when it comes to online entrepreneurship. What technology would be ideal and how to use that technology effectively? This is a big question.

(13) Financial Challenges :

Financial challenges are a lot different in India especially for online entrepreneurs. When we are starting out as an entrepreneur we don't opt for venture funding but try to go to funding for small to medium business people. Many such non-technical business people don't understand the online business models as a whole and so getting an initial business funding from them becomes challenging. The other option you can think of is a loan but bank loan is not at all an option in India for new online entrepreneurs.

(14) Negative Attitude :

The environment in the family, society and support system is not conducive to encourage rural people to take startup entrepreneurship as a career. It may be due to lack of awareness and knowledge of startup entrepreneurial opportunities. The young and well educated mostly tend to leave. As per circumstances, rural people by force may be more self-sufficient than their urban counterparts, but the culture of entrepreneurship tends to be weak. Continuous motivation is needed in case of rural employee which is sometime difficult for an entrepreneur to Rural Entrepreneurs are playing very important role in the development of economy. They face various problems in day to day work.

Opportunities for Indian Startup Entrepreneurs

Startup entrepreneurs' have great opportunities in India which are as under :

1. Free entry into the world trade.
2. Government has made its procedure very simple and easy.
3. Promotion of healthy competition in India.
4. Benefits of specialization.
5. Social and cultural development.
6. Easier exit.
7. Tax exemption for 3 years.
8. Easier patent filings.
9. Emerging digital opportunity
10. Patent Protection (Fast Tract Application)
11. Cyber security services to protect enterprises.
12. Career opportunities for youngsters.
13. Great incubator startup program.
14. Creation of new idea in Education and Health Care.

CONCLUSION

The startup program is a job creating program rather than job seeking program for the entrepreneurs. The country's economic environment must be favorable for organization to achieve efficiencies in today's global market. It should enable the startup entrepreneurs to provides a magical touch in achieving speed, flexibility, innovativeness and strong sense of

selfdetermination. They bring a new vision to the forefront of economic growth of a country. The startup entrepreneur have great opportunities for increasing the national income by creating new jobs and acts as a positive force in the economic growth by serving as a bridge between innovation and market place. Coming up with a start idea is very relevant thing for someone aiming for an independent work life. But implementing the idea is a big challenge which gradually gives rise to a challenges for the entrepreneurs.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Brijesh Patel and KiritChavda (2013), *Rural Entrepreneurship in India, Challenges andProblems*, International Journal of Advance Research in Computer Science andManagement Studies, ISSN : 2321-7782, Vol.-1, Issue-2, July 2013.
- [2]. Keshav Kumar (2015), *Indian Startups : Can they stand up against the world*, InternationalJournal of Advance Research in Computer Science and Management Studies, ISSN : 23217782, Vol.-3, Issue-4, April 2015.
- [3]. A Pilot Study on Technology Based Startups by Centre for International Trade inTechnology Indian Institute of Foreign Trade.
- [4]. NandanwarKalpana P. (2011), *Role of Rural Entrepreneurship in Rural Development*,International Referred Research Journal, ISSN-0974-2832, Vol. II, Issue-26, March.
- [5]. SaxenaSandeep. (2012), *Problems Faced By Rural Entrepreneurs and Remedies to SolveIt*, Journal of Business and Management, ISSN 2278-487X, Vol. 3, Issue 1, July-August.
- [6]. Santhi N. and Rajesh Kumar S. (2011), *Entrepreneurship Challenges and Opportunities inIndia*,Bonfring International Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management Science, Vol. 1, Special Issue, December.
- [7]. KishorChoudhary. (2011), *Effect of Globalization on Rural Entrepreneurship in India*, HalfYearly Global Economic Research Journal, ISSN 2249- 4081, Vol. I, Issue, pp. 88-92.
- [8]. www.iosrjournals.org
- [9]. <http://www.scribd.com/doc/26661470/Rural-Entrepreneurship-in-India>